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DESIGNING AN ESP GASTRONOMY COURSE

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ABSTRACT

English is currently an increasing medium of instruction for higher education in Western Europe, no matter the kind of college or higher educational institution we refer to. This is a result of the fact that most of the bibliography suggested as complimentary material and as authentic literature is increasingly written in English. This paper tries to describe the possibilities of establishing a linkage between the ESP lecturers on the one hand, and the content lecturers as well as the practitioners in gastronomy industry, on the other hand. One of the objectives of the ESP lecturers is the attempt to predict if the tasks and activities in the ESP class are relevant or appropriate for the students in their gastronomy career.

KEY WORDS: gastronomy course, content lecturer, English for Specific Purposes (ESP).

INTRODUCTION

The world around us is changing. Technology is changing, the needs of the gastronomy industry are changing, and the students coming into the gastronomy industry are changing. How is gastronomy education responding to these changes? What kind of paradigm shift is required in the way we educate future gastronomy chefs and managers that goes beyond coping with results in innovation and leadership? These questions represent the essence of gastronomy education for the 21st century.

The tourism and hospitality industry in general have an important role in the development of the economy of a society. The Republic of North Macedonia is a considerably small country with a powerful potential of development of modern standards in the field of gastronomy. It offers excellent, traditional cuisine and all this combined with beautiful lakes, mountain regions, and wide valleys with a moderate climate - perfect opportunities for summer and winter tourism. Thus, the crucial questions to the gastronomy profession are

the following: are we able to take the role of a powerful, but responsible actor, or do we accept the role of a reactor? Are we willing to interact with society or are we looking inwards?

The way gastronomy studies are taught round the world, even in Southeastern Europe, a much more restricted area - is subject to a great deal of variation in such aspects as the different emphases given to subjects such as dietetics, basics in cookery, restaurant management, traditional cuisine, etc. In order to equip the students with the needed knowledge of English, it is to establish a close connection between the ESP lecturer and the content lecturer.

According to certain authors (Gonzalez, 2000), ESP is necessarily a more specialized market than the larger area of English as a Foreign or Second Language. ESP lecturers find themselves in a situation where they are expected to produce a course that exactly matches the needs of a group of learners, but are very often expected to do so with no, or very limited preparation time. Then, they have to rely on the scarce resources to which they are accustomed.

The students at the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality in Ohrid have the possibility of choosing between three different branches: tourism, restaurant management and gastronomy. Each of these is further subdivided into more specialized sub-branches. The undergraduate students of tourism and hospitality have needs for English at this stage of their practical training (being involved in the management of the hotels, restaurants in the Ohrid area during the summer season) just as they will later on, as postgraduate students, or professional tourism and hospitality managers will be meeting foreign colleagues or working for foreign firms and institutions in the field of gastronomy industry.

ESP lecturers do not work in isolation. Their message should be sent in the form most suited to the receiver, i.e. the student, stressing those facts that turn out to be relevant and ignoring those they consider irrelevant after gathering information from several different sources and filtering out the unnecessary. The three basic actors on which the education experience within a college/faculty of tourism and hospitality swivels, i.e. the student, the content lecturer and the ESP lecturer, play significant roles in the development of the content and culture of the disciplines/profession. The more coordination there is among these three parties, the better the experience will be. (Gonzalez, 2000:36).

The students are supposed to be much better qualified than their ESP lecturers in the content area /field, and the main aim is to strengthen the acquisition of new language resources in order to use appropriate expressions for specific gastronomy expressions. The good ESP lecturer is a good communicator - and, usually vice-versa, he/she should develop the learner's skills of reading, note-taking, summarizing in relation to specific tasks within the ESP program, preferably tasks involving the use of authentic materials.

NEEDS ANALYSIS

A language course cannot be designed, unless something is known about the students for whom the course is intended, because the program of study depends on the objectives of the students. Different levels of needs analysis can be achieved since each of the students can express their own need in mind. If the needs cannot be accurately established they cannot be analyzed. Thus, ESP lecturers should always bear in mind the fact that any conclusions concerning needs however well considered would be largely intuitive. Nevertheless, the more information available, the more detailed the needs analyses can be. In practice, most of the ESP teachers are not in a position to undertake a detailed needs analysis to ensure that their topics and additional teaching materials cover all the learners' needs.

ESP LECTURER / CONTENT LECTURER

Whereas the content lecturer should educate the student in the content and culture of the discipline or profession, the ESP lecturer's job is to support this training process by giving the student an English proficiency level high enough to enable the student to interact with professionals that belong to the same field. The main obstacles to this kind of achievement are usually time restrictions and limited resources. It is difficult to expect the ESP lecturer to be in a position to provide such a standard. While the content lecturer is an

"expert" in the students' field of study, the ESP lecturer, even though he or she may have experience in various academic or professional fields, is not usually an expert in that field. Therefore, the ESP lecturer will have to be careful not to move into areas of expertise and responsibility that clearly belong to the content lecturer. (Gonzalez, 2000, Brennan, M., & M. Van Naerssen, 1989).

Interdisciplinary collaboration is very important in designing an ESP gastronomy course. This refers to gathering information from different departments and different areas of knowledge aiming at the solution of making more appealing the gastronomy promotion. Moreover, it should be a strategy for gastronomy studies to follow the challenges of the modern society.

It is the role of the ESP lecturer to teach either English language or language skills associated with the subject or both, but not the subject itself. If ESP teachers are faced with a subject they consider quite unknown to them, then they are likely to question their self-confidence and ability to teach the specific English of that subject.

Some of the advantages of interdisciplinary collaboration are:

- it offers more flexibility to the regular language course; it widens the scope of the more traditional language course since it includes topics that are not usually considered within a traditional L2 curriculum.
- students are more motivated; it serves to satisfy students' vocational needs and they feel more confident at the end of their undergraduate studies with a specialized bibliography written in English in order to prepare their final project to get the degree.
- it is more rewarding for the teacher because in this way they may feel that they are preparing the students for 'real' life; it is a way to go into team-teaching with teachers from other disciplines;

There are disadvantages concerning the interdisciplinary collaboration like the need to conduct an analysis to detect the needs of the students; the demand for a greater competence from the teachers as well as continuous updating; the difficulty of obtaining appropriate teaching materials, which means extra work to supplement existing materials and to design new ones. Moreover, there is always a need to have extra-academic support (companies, institutions).

ESP LECTURER / OTHER FACTORS

When we refer to other factors we mean all those from which we can benefit in the way of improving our competence as ESP lecturers and, as a consequence of this improvement, help our students develop the most valuable communication skills. The first source of information may come from other teaching institutions. It is a good idea to know what other ESP lecturers do in institutions different from ours but with similar students. The second source of information can be programs for higher education that are supported by the EC. The European Community program in the field of higher education aims at improving the quality and the 'European dimension' of higher education through a broad range of activities. Student nobilities, academic nobilities, Erasmus plus program and other activities play a vital role in producing high quality human resources, and adapting them to the constantly emerging needs for novel qualifications, and educating future generations as citizens in a European context.

ESP LECTURER/ STUDENT

It is obvious that there are far more opportunities for acquisition of the target language in a country where that language is spoken than outside of one. The value of study abroad for gastronomy managers can be invaluable: enlarged horizons, enhanced career prospects as well as more highly developed language skills. An important degree of cooperation between the content lecturer, ESP lecturer and student would certainly provide a more satisfactory educational experience. However, in determining learners' language needs, one has to be careful to distinguish real, current needs (what are the student needs - content lecturers being the source of this information)²⁵. Both of them should be distinguished from student desires (what the student would like to be able to do with the languages) and teacher-created needs (what the ESP lecturer imagines is needed or would like to impose on the students).

²⁵ Although the potential employer may be able to specify needs at some gross level, he is a non-expert in analyzing communicative situations. Because of that this information will have to be wisely analyzed and interpreted by the ESP lecturer so that the output can be transferred directly to the learners.

MATERIALS

Materials play a vital role in ESP teaching. The outputs in terms of the students' communicative skills at the end of the course will heavily depend upon the inputs they receive mainly in the form of library books, recorded messages, etc.

Published ESP materials, which are very often distributed worldwide, may have certain advantages and disadvantages. First of all, they provide a shape and an organization. They may not cover the necessary topics for the course, which means that the ESP lecturer has to make efforts to supply target texts from a variety of sources. These materials will meet the requirements produced by needs analysis.

Most ESP materials are an attempt to insert specific subject content into an EFL framework, thus holding a link between a general EFL and ESP, which, perhaps, should not exist. The ESP teacher doesn't need an ESP material writer who has a textbook or course book but rather a bank of materials from which to draw inspiration.

The ESP courses at the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality have become quite consolidated courses, beginning with English for General Purposes at the first year of their studies and continuing with ESP courses for gastronomy, tourism and hospitality management in the following years. These courses provide an over-all shape to the learning, helping the students predict where they are going, how far they have already gone, and how far they have still to go. An additional advantage to these courses is the ESP lecturers' attempts to produce a file rather than a book for the students' needs. This has proved to enhance the teaching process in the classroom, providing a firm background where not only the instructor but the student as well, feels content and satisfied with the topics, language exercises and communicative activities.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we have tried to outline one of the possible ways of designing an ESP gastronomy course - although it deserves to be explored in greater detail. At the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality more and more students are required to read texts in English or to speak or write English both in their academic training and at work. Focusing on this motivating approach, an ESP lecturer has to carry in mind that the students' primary concern is success in

their chosen specialty areas, and that the ESP lecturer becomes more of an equal partner in the learning/teaching process.

REFERENCES:

- Abbot, G. "Encouraging communication in English: a paradox". *ELT Journal* 35:228-230.1991.
- Benson, P. *Teaching and Researching Autonomy in Language Learning*. Longman. London.2001.
- Blue, G. and Harun, M "Hospitality language as a professional skill", *ESP Volume 22*. Issue1:73.2002.
- Brennan, M.,&M.Van Naerssen. "Language and content in ESP". *ELT Journal* 43,196-205.Oxford:Oxford University Press. 1989.
- Brown, P. and Levinson, S. *Politeness*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.1978.
- Bugariski, R. *Jezik u društvu*. Beograd: Prosveta. 1986.
- Chambers, F."A Re-Evaluation of Needs Analysis in ESP", *ELT Journal*, 25-33.USA: Pergamon Press Ltd.1980.
- Coulthard, *MA Introduction to Discourse Analysis*. London: Longman. .1977.
- Fasold, R. *The Sociolinguistics of Language*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers. 1997.
- Gonzalez, J.A. In search of synergies in ESP: agents involved and their invaluable contribution". *Proceedings of the ESSE5-2000 Conference*. Helsinki. 2000.
- Jones, G.M"ESP Textbooks: Do they really exist?". *English for Specific Purposes*. 9, 89-93.1990.
- Kramsch, C. *Context and Culture in Language Teaching*, 2nd edition, 1994.
- Petrovska, I. "Communicative Strategies in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry in English and Macedonian.". In Perić, J. et al. (eds) *Tourism & Hospitality Industry 2004: New Trends in Tourism and Hospitality Management*. Opatija, pp.545-555. 2004.
- Swales, JESP: "The textbook problem", *ELT Journal* 1:11-23. USA: Pergamon Press Ltd.1980.